

ACTIVITY OF CREATIVE WORKS TO IMPROVE EDUCATION AND EDUCATIONAL WORKS.

Kasimjonova Marjona Alisher kizi

Student of Namangan state university

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the role of music culture in the development of our national culture and the formation of students' abilities and talents by teachers.

Keywords: ability, music, tradition, culture, youth, pedagogy, idea, time, research.

Manifesting the abilities and talents of students in all aspects, ensuring the priority of national and universal ideals and values and pedagogical factors, achieving harmony in the interaction of the individual, society and the environment, and the relationship between the student and the teacher, with deep human respect for the traditional "Master-student" relationship. Bringing to the basics is the main direction of humanization of education, which ensures mutual understanding and cooperation of the subjects of the educational process. Collaborative pedagogy allows to determine the research problem of the need to create theoretical and conceptual ideas of teaching and educating young people in the spirit of modern times.[1]

Music clubs unite children into one team based on their interests. Regardless of age, if the educator is a master of his work, his level of creativity will increase during communication with children.

The head of the circle should focus on ensuring the independence of education during his work. It is important that he fully studies the content of preschool and educational process in his field and organizes activities based on this. Only then, students will be attracted to the continuity of education, they will get to know the best of national traditions and the riches of world culture. It is known to everyone that in many developed countries, a creative approach is taken to the improvement of education and training, and in this regard, the issue of practical effectiveness is put in the first place, not limited to the scope of theoretical beliefs. But no matter how good the experiences of these countries are, we cannot blindly apply them to our reality. [2] Any modern methods of education will have a positive effect only if they are connected with our morals, manners, lifestyle, and values of our national traditions.

According to the "Musical culture" curriculum of general secondary schools, musical literacy consists not only of notation methods, but also the composition of the general musical knowledge of students, a set of general knowledge and concepts (musical forms, genres, performance of musical instruments, folk music), to teach them differences, local styles of national music, classical music, notation, etc.). [3] Therefore, with the help of expressive means of music, together with students, they learn to think imaginatively, logically, creatively, their literacy and imagination expand, and national consciousness is formed. Here, the means of expression are related to the content, character of the musical work, and the use of the means of expression in it. Image description, development, musical terms in music literacy: tempo, dynamic signs, harmony, tonalities, timbre, register, etc. are carried out.

Tempo or pace indicates the speed of movement in the development of a musical piece, divided into slow, medium and fast tempos. Students are divided into slow, medium and fast tempos, indicating the speed of movement. The character of each tempo needs to be conveyed

figuratively so that students feel the speed of movement as a means of expression. Slow tempos (Lento? Lago) are used to express large-scale images, sad, sad, melancholy, quiet, character. Or fast tempos (Vivo, Allegretto) represent small-sized images, agile, cheerful, cheerful, playful character. At the same time, timbre, dynamic characters and registers help to shape the above characters in human thinking. In the explanation of the lower register, together with the image of animals such as a large, rough-moving bear, an elephant, concepts such as sad, gloomy, gloomy, quiet, scary and terrible can appear in the imagination of students. It is not for nothing that they are expressed in musical instruments such as bass or contrabass.[4] On the contrary, the characteristic features of the upper register are cheerful, agile, cheerful, and playfulness, and the use of high-range instruments such as flutes and violins, which represent images such as rabbits, mice, and butterflies, helps to form figurative thinking.

These tools, without a doubt, create an opportunity to get extensive and detailed information about the studied works of art, to be influenced by them, to draw conclusions and to understand their essence. In particular, in the use of means of expression in musical activities, the selection of works with a different pictorial and performance character (contrast), comparing both of them with excerpts or listening in their entirety, separately describing the factors of musical perception, their positive influence on the formation of musical perception shows. [5] For example, A. Mansurov music, the song "Uzbekistan-Ona-onajon" with the poem by A. Kochimov and the music of R. Abdullaev with the poem by N. Narzullaev "Our Independence Tulips" in the process of listening and learning the works of the means of expression that preserve the character and mood of the works (tempo, rhythm, dynamics, timbre) by explaining the role in a simple and special way, it becomes possible to learn to perceive concepts such as celebration and joy, to awaken emotional experiences and imaginations corresponding to this mood, to form ideas such as peace of the country, development of the Motherland.

In the training of musical circles, the teacher has knowledge of musical theory and the following aspects of ideological education:

that our nation gained political independence due to independence;

that he had the opportunity to determine his own destiny in practice;

that there is an opportunity to study the original spiritual and historical roots of our people;

It is necessary to pay particular attention to the need to strengthen the independence of the Republic and ensure stability with the help of specific examples.

References:

1. Artikov T. Music teaching methodology. T. 2012. – P. 10.
2. Yunusov R. Basics of traditional Uzbek music. Text of lectures. Tashkent. 2000. -P.41.
3. General secondary education State educational standards and curricula. Development of education No. 6. T. East. 1999, pp. 46-85
4. Begmatov S. "The art of security". Study - methodical manual. 2007. – P. 28.
5. Fosilov J. and others. Formation of the student's spirituality. T. 2000. – P. 62.